

THE CLIMATE-HEALTH RISK AT WORK IN THE AMAZON (ALTAMIRA)

CLISEVE[©]

CLIMAT, SANTÉ, TRAVAIL

Summary report
CLISEVE[©] Altamira,
Amazon - Brazil - 2025

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LAPA
RESEARCH

Croissance bleue

SUMMARY REPORT

CLISEVE© ALTAMIRA, AMAZON, BRAZIL – 2025

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FUNAI
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DSEI
(Special Indigenous Health District)

Peace for Pará

SEMOVI
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CEREST
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ABOUT

CLISEVE® Climate. Health. Work

CLISEVE® (Climate, Health, Work) is an independent international platform dedicated to understanding and preventing the impacts of climate change on occupational health and the organization of work.

In the face of intensifying climate pressures, it connects scientific expertise, labor actors and decision-makers to produce actionable knowledge, strengthen organizational resilience, and protect workers' health.

Its approach is grounded in the concept of "climate-health risk at work", which links health, climate and social responsibility. By integrating this dimension into occupational health and safety policies, CLISEVE® highlights the interdependence between people's health, adaptive practices and the sustainability of sectors and territories.

CLISEVE®'s studies and solutions rely on:

field research,
social and environmental data,
interdisciplinary analysis,
stakeholder coordination,

to identify risk situations and propose concrete solutions tailored to professions, sectors and local contexts.

Its objective: to support the necessary transformations towards safer, fairer and more sustainable working environments in the face of climate challenge.

THE CO-FOUNDERS OF CLISEVE®

"CLISEVE® offers a common framework for understanding, preventing and acting on the climate-health risk at work, by bringing together economic, social and institutional actors".

Caroline Véran

Founder and CEO of Croissance Bleue, co-founder of CLISEVE®. Caroline supports companies in implementing positive impact strategies, reconciling economic robustness and sustainability.

"In the age of artificial intelligence, the production of first-hand data is an invaluable strategic asset".

Jean-François Véran

Professor of Anthropology at the Federal University of Rio de Janeiro (PPGECC-UFRJ) - Director of LAPA-Research - Laboratory of Applied Anthropology. Co-founder of CLISEVE®

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INTRODUCTION

CLISEVE© ALTAMIRA 2025 STUDY

CLISEVE© Altamira is a study in **applied social sciences**, built from the lived experience of outdoor work. Its approach is guided by a clear principle: to consider workers' perceptions, symptoms, and situated knowledge as reliable data, and to transform them into operational indicators. This methodological foundation follows the trajectory of the *Population Assessment Tool*, developed and applied since 2012 by Jean-François Véran and LAPA-Research within Médecins Sans Frontières (MSF), from which it inherits both the ethical and scientific framework.

The CLISEVE© Altamira study produces first-hand, evidence-based data, with the aim of translating workers' experience into concrete indicators for managing the **climate–health risk at work**. It combines scientific commitment – representative sampling, mixed methods (questionnaires, interviews, field observation), inclusion of hard-to-reach populations, and participatory validation with workers and local institutions – with operational purpose: to generate outputs directly usable by trade unions, companies, public decision-makers, and, of course, the workers themselves.

The central concept of “climate–health risk at work”, developed throughout this study, does not replace biomedical, meteorological or occupational health and safety approaches. It adds another register – a reading of climate from within the world of work. CLISEVE© Altamira documents how climate change affects bodies, tools, rhythms, activity continuity, and mental health, as lived by those directly involved. It builds a bridge between disciplines and risk-management frameworks by integrating what has so far remained invisible: situated perceptions, self-reported symptoms, resilience mechanisms, and adaptation strategies developed by the workers themselves.

 This document is a summary report, excerpted from the full scientific and operational report (210 pages).

This anchoring gives the CLISEVE© Altamira 2025 study a dual positioning. On the one hand, following the approach developed by Caroline Véran (Agence Croissance Bleue), it connects health, climate and social responsibility within organizations. On the other hand, it broadens the scope of occupational health and safety by explicitly integrating the climate factor, emphasizing that workers' health, productive continuity, sectoral sustainability and territorial attractiveness are inseparable.

Scientific framework and timeline – towards COP30

The CLISEVE© Altamira 2025 study is part of the **ANR CONTER Project** (ANR-21-CE41-0021) – Territorial Conflicts on Agricultural Expansion Fronts (Brazilian Amazon): Violence, Evictions and Political Domination – directed by Véronique Boyer (EHESS/CNRS, France). In this context, the climate dimension contributes to a broader reflection on territorial, social and political dynamics in the Amazon.

The initial publication, released ahead of **COP30** (Belém, 2025), seeks to inform debates on social justice, adaptation and occupational health, and to launch, together with partners in Altamira, local restitution workshops turning the community of exposure into a community of action. It aims to connect local diagnosis with global agendas of climate governance.

Conducting an interview by the Xingu River. Credit: Jean-François Véran. CLISEVE© Altamira, 2025.

ALTAMIRA: AMAZONIAN CROSSROADS AND CLIMATE-EXPOSURE TERRAIN

Altamira is a complex city. A crossroads on the Transamazonian Highway – the Marabá–Altamira section inaugurated in 1972 –, it is located in the state of Pará, on the banks of the Xingu River. The city is the administrative center of Brazil’s largest municipality (159,000 km²) and has 126,000 inhabitants. Its urbanization accelerated through successive waves of labour migration tied to major works: first the road, then the Belo Monte dam (2011–2019, final estimated cost R\$ 42 billion / ≈ €8 billion), officially presented as a “100% Brazilian project.”

Surrounding the urban core lie expanding agricultural frontiers – notably cocoa plantations, highly vulnerable to recent droughts – and large-scale gold-mining projects such as Belo Sun, whose concession remains disputed, notably on environmental grounds. Within the same urban and peri-urban space, Indigenous communities, long-standing *ribeirinho* (riverine) families along the Xingu – some displaced by project impacts – and residents of RESEX extractivist reserves (created in the 1990s to support sustainable extraction of Pará nuts, rubber and forest fruits) all converge on Altamira in search of public services, economic opportunities, administrative procedures and healthcare.

Socially, the Belo Monte project generated the Reassentamentos Urbanos Coletivos (RUC) – collective urban resettlements – which relocated thousands of families from flooded riverbanks to peripheral housing complexes, often remote and poorly connected to essential services. Designed under the Plano Básico Ambiental (PBA) – the Basic Environmental Plan intended to anticipate, mitigate and compensate for impacts – these relocations have redrawn the city’s social geography and reshaped access to rights.

The climate dimension now amplifies these vulnerabilities. The exceptional 2024 drought, officially recognized by municipal decrees No. 200/2024, 233/2024 and 249/2024, critically lowered the Xingu’s water level, worsened the fish scarcity already caused by the dam, and disrupted navigation and water supply. Cocoa plantations suffered massive losses. At the same time, uncontrolled burn-offs turned into major wildfires, saturating the city with smoke and hindering mobility; conversely, heavy rains have caused flooding and road disruption.

This sequence of climatic extremes has directly affected working conditions.

FROM OCCUPATIONAL RISK TO THE CLIMATE–HEALTH RISK AT WORK

Brazilian occupational-health regulations (NR, PGR, RENAST) effectively address so-called classic risks – accidents, poisoning, chemical exposure, ergonomic strain – but do not yet identify climate as a risk category. The CLISEVE© Altamira study highlights this gap, showing how climate change is already translating into work through measurable indicators: bodily symptoms, psychological distress, mobility barriers, loss of access to services, damaged tools, supply breakdowns, storage difficulties, disorganized rhythms, risk-taking in task execution, and loss of efficiency, productivity and sense of purpose.

The objective is not to create a new bureaucratic category, but to demonstrate that workers themselves produce, through lived experience, a set of indicators that complement and enrich conventional surveillance and prevention tools.

This methodological stance requires considering not only formal employment, but also the vast informal sector, which lies beyond existing risk-management policies and therefore faces heightened vulnerability.

CLISEVE© is both a study and an operational platform. Its concluding call is for stakeholders to join and share indicators while supporting their implementation – through protocols, workshops and practical tools – in the service of both public and private action.

In France, CLISEVE© broke ground in 2024 with a pioneering study in the winegrowing sector, which received the Vinexposium Paris 2024 Award for Best Eco-Responsible Project. It is now being extended to the entire French agricultural sector (2025–2028) within a collective dynamic involving trade unions, public institutions and private actors united to anticipate occupational climate–health impacts. An application project has also been submitted for the Lake Victoria region (Homa Bay, Kenya), and another is under study for the city of Rio de Janeiro.

METHODOLOGY

SAMPLE

- 899 adult respondents
- \approx 3.3% of the population active outdoors (IBGE 2023)
- Margin of error: \pm 3.2% – 95% confidence level
- Professions covered: agriculture, artisanal fishing, construction, transport/delivery, street vending, urban cleaning, gold panning, specialized services

DATA COLLECTION

- Quantitative: questionnaires administered face-to-face (March 10–23, 2025) in city centers, hard-to-reach peripheries (RUC, gold panning areas, construction sites) and mediation spaces (union and association offices)
- Qualitative: 30 semi-structured interviews with workers, representatives from unions, and institutions, conducted beforehand to prepare the study and during data collection to contextualize the results

TREATMENT

- Real-time validation
- Descriptive analyses
- Correlations (χ^2 , Fisher)
- Multivariate Models (Stata/R)
- Significance threshold: $p < 0.05$

PARTICIPATORY APPROACH

- Active inclusion of hard-to-reach populations (gold mining areas, Belo Monte bridge construction sites)
- Participation agreements with trade unions, associations and institutions
- Feedback will be provided to local stakeholders through workshops.
- Production of professional fact sheets usable by organizations and workers

TEAM

- Coordination: two researchers (UFRJ-UERJ)
- 10 junior researchers from Altamira (UFPA / UEPA / Serra Dourada) trained by the coordination
- A psychologist and a social worker provided assistance, support, and guidance to respondents in difficult situations.

ETHICS

- Informed consent
- Data anonymization
- Psychological support, medical referrals and social support for respondents in difficulty

Researchers in the field. Credit: Jean-François Véran. CLISEVE© Altamira, 2025.

WHO ARE THE OUTDOOR WORKERS?

47.5% of respondents work in rural areas, even though the study was conducted largely in Altamira’s hyper-central zone. This confirms that the city is not an isolated urban enclave but rather the nerve center of an agricultural and extractive hinterland. Farmers, fishers, and gold miners converge here to access public services, markets, and institutions.

The six dominant occupations (Table 1) account for two-thirds of the sample: agriculture/livestock (30.1%), artisanal fishing (13.2%), street trade (11.2%), construction (11.2%), transport/delivery (10.2%), and specialized services (10.1%). The latter category includes mechanics and repair work (mechanics, electricians, glaziers), maintenance activities (fuel attendants, technicians), and outdoor proximity services (activity leaders, health professionals, teachers, or itinerant sales representatives). These professions, represented in the sample of outdoor workers, illustrate how climate exposure now extends to a range of typically urban needs still anchored in open-air conditions. Garis (urban cleaning agents) and gold miners complete this landscape of outdoor labour, strongly dependent on weather conditions.

Nearly 70% of workers have a low-protection employment status (Figure 1). The local labour market is primarily structured around self-employment (48.7%), informality (13.9%), and daily contracts (6.8%). Formal employment remains marginal—10,8% on permanent contracts, 6.3% in the public sector, and 4.9% on fixed-term contracts. This socio-economic structure reflects a fabric dominated by precariousness and self-employment, with minimal social protection against climate-related risks.

10.2% of respondents are motorcycle-taxi drivers, highlighting the significance of constrained mobility. Collective urban relocations (RUCs), created after the Belo Monte project, impose daily journeys that often exceed an hour on foot or require costly motorised transport. River crossings (shuttles, ferries) add waiting and navigation time under open-air conditions. Here, movement itself is not neutral—it already constitutes a form of exposure.

72% of respondents are men (Figure 2). The gender imbalance is pronounced, especially in transport, construction, and gold mining, which are almost exclusively male sectors. Women are present in agriculture and artisanal fishing, but their outdoor activities—food vending, care services, street work—remain largely invisible in official classifications. The imbalance observed in the sample reflects the fact that the CLISEVE© study deliberately focuses on the category of “work,” excluding many activities not conventionally recognised as such. Numerous female activities—particularly those performed outside the home—thus fell outside the observation scope. This calls for a dedicated CLISEVE© study to make these activities visible and integrate them into the analysis of climate–health risks at work.

17.7% of workers are aged 60 or older and continue to engage in demanding outdoor occupations—agriculture, fishing, or street trade. Their continued presence in these sectors reflects both economic necessity and the lack of alternatives, intensifying climate vulnerability linked to ageing bodies and minimal social protection.

 Nearly 70% of outdoor workers have a low-protection status.

Figure 1. Distribution of the professional situation of the respondents (N=899)— CLISEVE© Altamira, 2025.

 Outdoor work is not merely a working condition – it structures climate vulnerability in Altamira.

47.5% of outdoor workers are rural: Altamira is not an urban enclave.

28% of respondents are women: an acknowledged bias that highlights the lower visibility of women's outdoor work

Table 1. Main occupations and activities of respondents (N=899) – CLISEVE© Altamira, 2025.

PROFESSIONS / ACTIVITIES	NUMBER OF CITATIONS (N)	FREQUENCY (%)
Agriculture / Livestock	271	30,1
Artisanal Fishing	119	13,2
Street Activities / Vending	101	11,2
Construction	101	11,2
Transport / Taxi / Delivery	92	10,2
Specialized Services	91	10,1
Garbage Collectors / Cleaning Agents	44	4,9
Mining / Gold Panning	37	4,1
Security	31	3,4
Formal commerce	22	2,4
Students	9	1
Retired	3	0,3
Total Observations	899	100

One in six workers identifies as black, one in ten as indigenous: an overrepresentation that shows that the health-climate risk at work is permeated by racial inequalities.

Figure 2. Distribution of outdoor workers by sex and occupational sector (N=899) – CLISEVE© Altamira, 2025.

Table 2. Color/race: comparison IBGE* vs external actives (white/pardo/preto/native) (N=899) – CLISEVE© Altamira, 2025.

IBGE Category	CLISEVE© 2025	Total IBGE Population 2022 (%)
White	11% (n=99)	166
Pardo (mixed)	57.6% (n=518)	724
Indigenous	10.5% (n=94)	29
Black (preto)	16.9% (n=152)	76
Others**	4.0% (n=36)	–
Total observations	899	100

* The racial categories used follow the official census classification of the IBGE (*Instituto Brasileiro de Geografia e Estatística*), the Brazilian national statistics agency responsible for the census. This classification is based on self-identification.

** The category "Others" refers to a self-classification distinct from the IBGE categories, such as "Amazonian", "caboclo" or the unique choice of a community category like ribeirinho (riverine).

Black and Indigenous workers are overrepresented (Table 2).

Pretos (Black) account for 16.9% of the sample (compared with 7.6% in Altamira’s general population, IBGE 2022), and Indigenous respondents make up 10.5% (vs. 2.9%). In contrast, White workers represent only 11% (vs. 16.6%, IBGE). These disparities confirm a racial segmentation of the outdoor labour market, rooted in historical inequalities that have assigned Black and Indigenous populations to the most precarious and exposed occupations. It is important to note that identification as preto (Black) derives from respondents’ self-declaration, as CLISEVE© adopted the official and mandatory census categories of the Brazilian Institute of Geography and Statistics (IBGE).*

37.5% of respondents identify as belonging to a traditional community (Table 3): *ribeirinhos*,

Indigenous peoples, or residents of extractive reserves. The category *colonos* (settlers) refers to farmers who settled along the Transamazonian Highway in the 1970s as part of Brazil’s agricultural colonization program and who often work for landowners. It emerged in our study through respondents’ self-identification (n=79). However, it is not officially recognised among the “traditional peoples and communities” defined by Brazilian legislation (Federal Decree No. 6,040). This reveals a gap between institutional classifications and certain local modes of self-definition. Its inclusion here is justified by the fact that *colonos*, like traditional communities, maintain livelihoods directly dependent on the natural environment and are therefore particularly exposed to the effects of climate change.

The plurality of identity affiliations revealed by the study reflects the profound social transformations triggered by the Belo Monte dam and the ensuing forced displacements. Many *ribeirinhos* and Indigenous people now engage in precarious urban occupations – street vending, construction, cleaning, transport – while continuing to define themselves by their community origins. Attachment to these traditional identities, despite the loss of associated living environments, represents both a form of symbolic resistance and a means of accessing specific rights within the framework of the Environmental Basic Plan (PBA). In Altamira, these multiple – community-based, professional, and administrative – identifications, which sometimes overlap, form an intricate web of plural belongings where cultural assertion, the search for recognition, and constrained adaptation to climatic and socio-economic transformations intersect.

37.5% of respondents report belonging to traditional communities or to groups particularly exposed due to their direct dependence on the natural environment.

Table 3. Traditional community or group of affiliation (self-reported) (N=899) – CLISEVE© Altamira, 2025.

COMMUNITY OR GROUP	NUMBER OF CITATIONS (N)	FREQUENCY (%)
<i>Ribeirinhos</i> (Riverside Communities)	160	178
Indigenous Peoples	94	105
Extractivists	19	21
<i>Colonos</i> (settlers)	79	88

- In Altamira, the vulnerability of outdoor workers emerges from the convergence of precarious employment status, constrained mobility, active ageing, the invisibility of women’s work, racial segmentation, and environmental dependence. Together, these elements form a matrix of exposure in which outdoor labour constitutes the structuring factor of what we define as the climate–health risk at work.

CLIMATE PERCEPTION: A COMMUNITY OF OPINION

79.1% of respondents fully agree that the climate situation is alarming (and 11.2% partially agree); 73.3% fully agree that urgent action is needed, and 68.2% fully recognise the human origin of climate change (Figure 3). This threefold finding reveals a strong pattern: in Altamira, climate awareness is primarily an empirical knowledge, shaped daily by how the climate directly affects each person's work.

This broad agreement results in a clear consensus: 85% of respondents endorse at least two of the three dimensions—concern, urgency, and human origin. Skepticism remains marginal: only 2.6% reject all the statements proposed by the study, and about 13% express doubts regarding the human origin of climate change. Far from the ideological divides often seen in public debate, the shared experience of outdoor work is enough to anchor climate perception as a collective and self-evident reality.

A transversal awareness: statistical tests show that no major social variable—age, gender, race, or community affiliation—produces significant differences. Men and women, the young and the elderly, Black, mixed-race, or Indigenous workers converge on the same assessment.

LINES OF VARIATION: OCCUPATIONS AND INTERPRETATIONS

The only divergences concern the human origin of climate change. Fishers and transport workers, confronted with dwindling fish stocks and growing mobility constraints, strongly adhere to the idea of a human origin for climate change. Farmers, by contrast, are more ambivalent: some invoke natural cycles, others divine will — “it has always been this way,” “only God decides.” Street workers, more absorbed by the immediate urgencies of daily life and with limited access to information, appear more hesitant. These nuances, however, do not call into question the essential point: climate awareness remains a widespread social fact, rooted in the direct experience of outdoor work.

ENVIRONMENTAL MEMORY AND NEW CLIMATE AWARENESS

The recent memory of the social and environmental impacts of the Belo Monte dam remains a structuring force, with the compensation measures of the Environmental Basic Plan (PBA) having been at the center of social mobilisations, political attention, and technical impact assessments.

Within this context, the climate issue emerged more recently, now taking shape in its own specificity through the acceleration of extreme events — the droughts of 2023 and 2024, floods, and fires.

The emerging climate awareness revealed by the study's data does not follow the lines of conflict opened by Belo Monte and the management of its compensations; rather, it unfolds transversally, encompassing all social groups. Lived experience thus seems to transcend partisan affiliations in a municipality whose voting patterns remain largely conservative. Here, climate consciousness arises less from political discourse than from the concrete articulation between environment and work: the scarcity of fish, disruption of harvests, and longer journeys made harder by climatic hazards. This shift — from conflict to lived experience — turns the climate issue into a new shared language.

INTERNATIONAL COMPARISON

The comparison with data collected in French vineyards as part of CLISEVE© Wine Sector – France (2024) confirms this diagnosis. In both contexts, a clear majority recognises the existence and urgency of climate change. However, the intensity of responses is more pronounced in Altamira: the proportion of farmers declaring themselves “completely in agreement” with the proposed statements reaches 80% in Altamira versus 68.5% in France, a difference of 10 to 15 points. This gap may reflect the combined effect of Altamira's particularly acute environmental experience and the exceptional droughts of 2023 and 2024, with their direct impacts.

In Altamira, outdoor work forges a shared climate awareness that transcends professional and social differences.

Figure 3. Degree of agreement with climate statements (N=899) – CLISEVE© Altamira, 2025.

Figure 4. Degree of agreement to climate statements (key figures) (N=899) – CLISEVE© Altamira, 2025.

FARMERS: ALTAMIRA VS FRANCE (CLISEVE© VITICULTURE 2024)

- Climate concern: 80% in Altamira vs 60% in France.
- Urgency to act: 69% vs 58%.
- Farmers in Altamira express a sharper sense of climate concern, likely reinforced by cumulative environmental impacts and two consecutive years of exceptional drought.

● **Conclusion:** In Altamira, climate is an integral part of the work experience. Droughts, extreme rainfall, or wildfire smoke are mentioned with the same immediacy as fatigue or health. From this shared experience emerges a community of opinion. CLISEVE© makes it possible to qualify this experience in scientific and operational terms, embedding it within a framework of indicators that connects daily life, social recognition, and public action.

IMPACT OF CLIMATE CHANGE ON WORK

Climate is not a backdrop: it intervenes in rhythms, productivity, mobility, and tools. In Altamira, it reshapes the concrete organisation of work.

2023–2024: NO CHANGE OBSERVED... FOR 1.6% OF RESPONDENTS.

Our reference period covers the past two years (since 2022), marked by exceptional climatic events. Nearly all outdoor workers report having noticed changes, citing on average five to six types of disruption. The emphasis falls on late 2023 and 2024, when the municipality officially declared climate emergencies (Decrees No. 2993/2023 and No. 3757/2024). This represents the first application of the CLISEVE© study using an “event-based” climate format.

Figure 5. Changes observed by workers (N=899) – CLISEVE© Altamira, 2025.

MAPPING OF PERCEIVED ENVIRONMENT-CLIMATE CO-IMPACTS (2023–2024)

- Drought and smoke (2024)**
 Municipal decree no. 3757/2024: water emergency (> 3,700 families).
 Vegetation fires and persistent smoke.
- Low water levels of the Xingu River (2023)**
 Decree No. 2993/2023 (drought, heat waves, record low water levels).
 Sudden rises linked to the Belo Monte valves (ANA – Bulletin 2023-2024).
- Heavy rainfall / flash floods**
 Rapid flooding of the Xingu, flooding of roads and low-lying houses. (Municipal Civil Defense, 2024).

Figure 5 illustrates the extent and diversity of climate change impacts perceived by outdoor workers. The most frequently reported phenomena concern heat (73.3%) and intensified droughts (71.7%), followed by disturbances in the water cycle—irregular rainfall (62.2%) and flooding (41%). Other hazards, such as increased fires (38.9%) and storms (21.3%), reflect the growing prevalence of extreme events.

Beyond meteorological disturbances, respondents describe a continuum of impacts affecting human health (rising illnesses 42.6%, difficulties in accessing water 34.5%), agriculture (declining soil productivity 35.8%), and animal life (decline in fish populations 49.2%, disappearance of wildlife 28.5%, suffering of domestic animals 24.8%). These perceptions encompass the entire living environment, highlighting the interconnection between health, ecosystems, and professional practices.

MAPPING CO-IMPACTS: EVIDENCE DRAWN FROM LIVED EXPERIENCE

In Altamira, workers describe a shared experience in which increased heat, prolonged drought, and irregular rainfall overlap with variations in the Xingu River caused by the regulation of the Belo Monte dam. These combined phenomena affect fishing, river mobility, and the organisation of work.

This mapping of co-impacts, now recognised by IBAMA – Brazil’s federal environmental agency – in its recent demand for a revision of the water flow released by Belo Monte ([Pública, 2025](#)), echoes the empirical evidence produced by the study.

EXPERIENCE FORMS A SHARED DIAGNOSIS OF CLIMATE AT WORK

Men and women perceive the increase in heat and the prolongation of droughts in roughly the same proportions ($\approx 73\text{--}75\%$). Younger respondents mention drought slightly more often (45% among those aged 18–24 versus 36% among those aged 65–79), but the gap remains small; irregular rainfall is cited by about 62% across all age groups ($p > 0.10$). Among IBGE color/race groups, responses vary little ($\approx 70\text{--}82\%$). Indigenous and ribeirinho respondents fall within the same range as other inhabitants.

In sum, the community of opinion regarding climate change here extends into a community of perception at work: lived experiences and representations of climate converge.

“*Today I was lucky—there was no smoke. Yesterday, you could hardly see anything; driving was impossible. On the road, the smoke was everywhere, we were riding blind.*”
(Motorcycle taxi driver, 26 years old)

Fishing

- Reduced fishing windows: **$\approx 58\%$** of fishers report shortening their working hours due to heat or river
- Declining catches: **87.4%** report “far fewer fish,” often linking this to drought and fluctuating water levels.

Transport

- Smoke / reduced visibility: **55.3%** of motorcyclists report episodes when it is “impossible to circulate.”
- Delays and disrupted routes: **50.4%** of motorcycle users report frequent delays; **47.7%** mention flooded or damaged streets.

FISHING, TRANSPORT, CONSTRUCTION... EVERY OCCUPATION FEELS THE EFFECTS OF CLIMATE

The reported constraints reflect tangible disruptions to activity across all sectors studied. In fishing, variations in river levels restrict fishing windows and alter catch cycles. Transport is marked by episodes of smoke and flooding that disrupt traffic and lengthen travel times. On construction sites and in mining, sudden rainfall interrupts work and heightens risks associated with waterlogged soils. In agriculture, heat and adverse weather shorten working days and reduce yields.

These constraints describe a work dynamic now structured by climatic conditions, where each occupation must adapt to its own specific forms of instability.

“*It’s worse now — we can no longer navigate, the river has turned into a sheet of mud. Before, we could still pass through the sand, but now it’s blocked. The fish have disappeared: there’s no more food, no more trees to drop seeds.*” (Fisher, 59 years old)

Construction / gold mining

- Interruptions during rain events: **50.5%** of construction workers and **54.1%** of gold miners report flash floods as a cause of work stoppage.
- Increased risk of accidents due to waterlogged soils: approximately **one-third** of workers in these sectors.

Agriculture

- Heat and adverse weather: **44.3%** of producers report workdays interrupted due to extreme climatic conditions.
- Degraded soils: **44.6%** observe a decline in agricultural yields linked to drought and loss of soil moisture.

HEAT AND DECLINING YIELDS

Three-quarters of respondents report a decline in productivity linked to heat (63.2% significant; 12.7% moderate).

Heat also emerges as a factor of reduced productive efficiency (Figure 6). Task performance and work continuity are disrupted. The decline in productivity thus reflects the immediate impact of climate on the concrete organisation of work, regardless of the technical conditions or sectors considered in the study.

Figure 6. Perceived impact of heat on productivity (N=899) – CLISEVE© Altamira, 2025.

Table 4. Body adjustments to heat (N=899) – CLISEVE© Altamira, 2025.

Bodily Adjustment	Percentage (%)
More frequent breaks	61,4
Slower pace	56,5
Interrupted workdays	43,1
Extended tasks	26,8
Loss of job satisfaction	19,0

THE BODY AS THE FIRST LEVER OF ADAPTATION

The responses are remarkably consistent across professions ($\chi^2 = 8.9$; $df = 8$; $p > 0.1$): heat is primarily managed through bodily adjustments – breaks and slower pace – then results in interrupted workdays and extended tasks, and finally in a loss of job satisfaction. This sequence outlines a coherent gradient from felt experience to productive impact.

Heat is initially managed through bodily adjustments (breaks, slower pace), before resulting in interruptions and longer tasks.

Some occupations show a higher rate of reported “no impact” (delivery, street vending, gold mining) – not due to greater resilience, but as a result of a more immediate constraint (selling or producing to survive day by day) that partially masks physical strain. “You just have to keep going.”

TOOLS AND MATERIALS UNDER CLIMATIC STRESS

Climate also weakens the tools, materials, and products of work. Nearly one in two respondents reports at least one material impact – breakdown, wear, alteration, or loss.

Resource (fishing)

Death or scarcity of fish
→ Fishing nets are increasingly coming up empty.

Wear and tear (transport)

Increased maintenance of engines and parts
→ Climate acts as a factor of mechanical wear and economic strain (repair costs).

Damaged products (agriculture, commerce)

Greater difficulties in storage and transport
→ Climate accelerates the deterioration of production.

TRANSPORT AS A CLIMATE EXPOSURE IN ITS OWN RIGHT

Daily mobility constitutes a specific form of exposure to climate–health risk. Motorcycles, walking, and river transport structure the mobility patterns of outdoor workers: 36.6%, 20.9%, and 18.8% of respondents respectively report using these as their main means of transport. Other forms of transport – bicycle, car, truck, or bus/van (≈3%) – remain marginal (Figure 7).

Statistical analysis reveals a strong dependence between the mode of transport and the type of impact reported ($\chi^2(120) = 844.76; p < 0.0001$). Each mode thus defines a distinct profile of vulnerability: smoke, heat, and flooding for motorcyclists; fluctuating water levels and accidents for river users; direct exposure to heat and rain for pedestrians. This stratification of mobility-related risks shows that in Altamira, moving to work already means working under potentially extreme climatic conditions (Figure 8).

Figure 7. Main mode of transport among outdoor workers (N=899) – CLISEVE© Altamira, 2025.

“When it’s too hot, the helmet burns, so we hang it on the handlebars. We ride with our heads uncovered, but after twenty minutes you can feel your skin burning. When the smoke comes, you can’t see anything – you have to stop. Even breathing becomes difficult.”
(Motorcycle taxi driver, 21 years old)

Figure 8. Climate impacts on travel, by main modes (N=899) – CLISEVE© Altamira, 2025.

What CLISEVE© Altamira reveals

- Outdoor work structures exposure to climate risk.
- Empirical thresholds of adaptation already exist in daily practices: people slow down, interrupt, or stop working.
- Transport under constraint has become a risk factor in itself – smoke, floods, low water levels, and degraded roads.
- The climate-related degradation of tools and materials increases vulnerability by compounding breakdowns, over-maintenance, and product losses.
- Logistics chains emerge as critical links, where moving and maintaining activity weigh as heavily as the work itself.
- In Altamira, climatic signals interact with the hydraulic regulation of Belo Monte: these are co-impacts, not a single causal chain.
- Climate-health risk at work takes shape through outdoor labour – in gestures, movements, tools, and the very organisation of work.

FOUR CATEGORIES OF CLIMATE-HEALTH RISK IN ALTAMIRA:

Assessing the health risks to which outdoor workers are exposed in the context of climate change requires a systemic and multidimensional approach.

Four categories of risks were identified within the framework of CLISEVE© Altamira:

Figure 9. Share of workers reporting at least one risk in each category (N=899) – CLISEVE© Altamira, 2025.

Physical (heat/drought): extreme heat, dehydration, heat stroke; difficulty accessing water.

Mental health: stress, anxiety, sleep disorders, persistent fatigue.

Infectious (rain/water/smoke): dengue and influenza; fungal infections and gastrointestinal skin problems related to stagnant water.

Chemicals (pesticides/mercury): fumes, particles, pesticides; less effective protection under high heat.

More than nine out of ten workers (92.2%) report being exposed to at least one climate-related risk.

On average, each respondent reports nearly two categories simultaneously (1.91), indicating widespread multiple exposure. This average does not vary significantly across occupations, although specialized services (2.19) and transport (2.02) appear slightly more exposed than agriculture (1.80).

METHODOLOGICAL NOTE

● **Anchoring periods:**

Dry season 2024 (Sept.–Dec., drought/smoke); rainy season 2025 (Jan.–Mar.). Collection: March 2025 (N = 899).

● **Self-referred symptoms:**

Physical, mental, infectious, chemical registers; multiple items; symptomatic counting by season.

● **Polyexposure:**

Thresholds ≥ 3 , ≥ 5 , ≥ 6 symptoms; seasonal comparison (average, asymptomatic, distribution).

● **Analyses:**

Descriptive, chi²/Fisher; logistic (≥ 5 symptoms, dry season), age/sex controls, 95% CI.

● **Biomedical alignment:**

Observed patterns (thermal, infectious, chemical) are consistent with the literature; perceptions align with known mechanisms → strengthened validity (see full report).

DRY SEASON 2024: MULTIPLE EXPOSURE AND “TIPPING POINT”

The 2024 dry season was marked by a high concentration of heat-related symptoms (Heatmap 1). Headaches (66.7%) were the most frequently reported, followed by dehydration (33.5%), heat strokes (17.9%), and respiratory disorders (13.7%). Each worker reported an average of 3.1 symptoms, nearly double that of the rainy season (1.83). Asymptomatic cases became rare – only 12%, compared to 25% during the rainy period. More than one in two workers experienced at least three simultaneous symptoms, and 15% reported six or more.

With the 2025 rains, the risk did not disappear – it shifted, driven this time by respiratory infections, disease vectors, and stagnant water.

This seasonal alternation illustrates a continuum of exposure, in which climate–health risk does not pause but changes form according to environmental conditions.

One in three outdoor workers reported dehydration and dizziness during the 2024 drought.

Heatmap 1. Comparison of symptoms: 2025 rainy season vs. 2024 drought (N=899) – CLISEVE© Altamira, 2025.

DRY SEASON AND SYMPTOMS: DIFFERENCES ACROSS SECTORS

Transport and delivery

Increased risk of multiple exposures: more than one in five exceeds the threshold of ≥ 5 symptoms, dominated by headaches (**72%**), fatigue (**48%**) and dehydration (**44%**).
 Factors: constant mobility, continuous physical effort and lack of time regulation.

Garbage collectors/maintenance

Accumulation of severe symptoms: headaches (**79%**), dizziness (**44%**), dehydration (**42%**).
 Working conditions on the street, associated with
 Factors: prolonged exposure and chronic heat fatigue.

Agriculture

Maximum thermal exposure: heat stroke and fatigue (**46%**), flu (**45%**), headaches (**60%**).
 Factors: physiological overload related to prolonged effort in extreme conditions.

Construction

Mixed symptomatic profile: heat stroke (**35%**), flu (**52%**), headache (**58%**), combining thermal and infectious conditions.
 Factors: combination of dust, exertion, and direct exposure.

Street vending

Marked fragility: headaches (**70%**), dizziness (**37%**), fatigue (**32%**), often cumulative in the dry season.

Factors: thermal overload linked to prolonged exposure to full sun and precarious shelter conditions.

Gold mining

Less thermal stress (**19%** heat stroke), but high infectious vulnerability (flu **44%**, malaria/dengue/Zika **8%**).

Factors: proximity to stagnant water and isolation of sites.

Artisanal fishing

Profile of thermal and muscular exhaustion: headaches (**62%**), fatigue (**48%**), dizziness (**29%**) and respiratory problems (**22%**).

Factors: long days on the water, without shade or access to hydration.

“*The time limit is clear: 11 a.m. is the maximum – after that come fainting spells and dizziness. It's impossible to work in the fields.*”
(Farmer, 42 years old)

VULNERABILITIES, MAINLY SOCIAL

Occupational sector

The pattern is transversal (all professions are exposed), yet each sector displays its own symptomatic imprint.

Gender (dry season)

Multiple exposure (≥ 5 symptoms) affects **19.1%** of women compared with **13.2%** of men, indicating slightly heavier exposure among women.

Age / color-race

No significant differences observed → the risk cuts across generations and IBGE “color/race” categories.

PERCEPTION AND SYMPTOMS: THE SAME SIGNAL

47% of workers reporting five or more symptoms also consider the impact of climate on their work to be “extremely noticeable.” This correlation shows that perception is not merely an opinion – it directly reflects the intensity of physical strain.

Climate–health risk at work is grounded in a shared field of exposure, within which each sector expresses a particular form of vulnerability.

What CLISEVE© Altamira reveals

- The exceptional drought of 2024 triggered a symptomatic explosion: nearly nine out of ten workers reported at least one heat-related disorder, and more than half experienced three or more – headaches, dehydration, dizziness, heat strokes. The data demonstrate the direct health burden of this extreme climatic episode.
- Climate–health risk at work persists year-round: thermal during the 2024 drought and infectious during the 2025 rainy season (flu, dengue, fungal infections, digestive disorders).
- Perception and symptoms converge: the more symptoms workers present, the more strongly they perceive the impact of climate on their health.
- Vulnerabilities stem primarily from outdoor work and organisational conditions that determine whether – and to what extent – workers can protect themselves from climatic exposure.
- CLISEVE©’s contribution: using local data, the tool highlights the materiality of climate–health risk in outdoor work – measuring how bodily strain, symptoms, and perceptions interconnect with the concrete conditions of work and its organisation.

MENTAL HEALTH AND CLIMATE-HEALTH RISK

The risk factor is not outdoor work itself, but the climatic extreme.

Working outdoors is not, in itself, a risk to mental health: as the data on farmers show, contact with nature can even enhance one’s sense of purpose and job satisfaction. But in Altamira, climatic extremes – heat, smoke, low water levels, intense rainfall – disrupt these balances. Fatigue, anxiety, and discouragement are on the rise, coexisting with contentment and a strong sense of determination. This ambivalence reflects an “everyday resilience” – the ability to endure despite the emotional overload imposed by an increasingly unpredictable environment. Mental health thus emerges as an integral component of climate–health risk at work.

Figure 11. Distribution of emotional states (N=899) – CLISEVE© Altamira, 2025.

METHODOLOGY

- Questions focused on current emotional state at work (the two weeks preceding the interview) to limit retrospective bias (Kahneman & Riis, 2005).
- The “content/happy” option was added after the pilot phase, following field feedback from the research team. A psychologist trained the field researchers in identifying at-risk behaviours.
- A psychologist and a social worker provided assistance, support, and referral for respondents experiencing difficulties.
- The system operated under an active case detection approach (MSF reference, Véran 2020).

As shown in Figure 10, the distribution of emotional states cannot be reduced to a simple well-being/suffering axis. Fatigue (~31%, n = 278) dominates the negative signals, often associated with insomnia and the strain of mobility and informal work. The positive spectrum remains predominant: content/happy 49.5% (n = 443), determined ~29% (n = 257), sometimes organised. This reflects an ordinary resilience – the ability to “keep going” under constraint.

Anxiety (n = 57), sadness (n = 58), and despair (n = 26) remain minority but significant states; suicidal thoughts (n = 2) and alcohol/drug use (n = 4), though marginal, are not anecdotal: they indicate breaking points where multiple – and potentially climate-related – pressures accumulate.

Figure 10. Distribution of main emotional states (N=899) – CLISEVE© Altamira, 2025.

Suicidal thoughts: n = 2

Figure 12. Distribution by overall emotional score (N=899) – CLISEVE© Altamira, 2025.

PROFILES AND SOCIAL VULNERABILITIES

Distress, gray zone, and well-being: a topology of vulnerability

The population-based screening tool with differentiated weightings, the emotional score (Figure 12), is designed to identify risk profiles rather than make individual diagnoses. It is based on a contextual approach to emotional well-being, distinct from clinical scales (Schwarz & Clore, 2007; Courtenay, 2000; Fredrickson, 2001). The full methodological note is included in the complete edition of the CLISEVE© Altamira 2025 report.

Gray zone: 19.2% (n = 172)

A silent fragility (average score -1.3; range -2.5 to -0.5), characterised by fatigue (**~90%**) and recurrent anxiety. Mostly self-employed or informal workers, they operate in agriculture, fishing, or street-based activities, with limited access to healthcare and basic rights (**~4 mentions**, cf. p.35). More than two-thirds report a strong climatic impact, and nearly one-third consider giving up their activity. This zone reflects a latent imbalance, where precarity and fatigue accumulate without crossing the threshold into overt distress.

Core distress group: 4.4% (N = 39)

These workers combine high physical exposure, precarious employment status (54% self-employed, 31% informal), and limited access to rights (**~3.7 mentions**). Their perception of climatic impact is very strong (**77%**), accompanied by high intentions to quit (**39%**), with heat cited as a decisive factor for **62%** of them.

Severe symptoms – fatigue (**90%**), sadness (**50%**), headaches, and dizziness – add to multiple negative emotional states, sometimes including suicidal thoughts. Their vulnerability reflects a structural exhaustion, at the intersection of precarity, isolation, and climatic extremes.

Better-off group: 7.3% (N = 66)

A relatively protected group, characterised by stronger institutional integration (**18%** public servants, **~5 mentions** of rights). Perceived climatic impacts on work are rare (**14%**), and **26%** report no perceived effect at all. **61%** exclude the idea of leaving their job, reflecting a more stable sense of control. The symptom burden is low (0.35 symptom per person), limited to occasional fatigue.

These workers make greater use of information and training, supported by more active social networks and mutual aid – a form of relative resilience sustained by job stability and the symbolic recognition of their work.

TERRITORIAL IDENTITIES AND VULNERABILITIES

OPERATIONAL CONCEPTS IN THE ANALYSIS

- *Solastalgia (Albrecht, 2007)*
A feeling of loss linked to the degradation of one's territory, where environmental disruption erodes the sense of belonging and place-based identity. Solastalgia sheds light on the existential distress experienced in response to the transformation of landscapes – particularly acute among Indigenous and ribeirinho populations, for whom territory is simultaneously a place of life, work, and memory.
- *Eco-anxiety (Coffey et al., 2021; Pihkala, 2022)*
Helps explain the gray zone (~1/5) and intentions to quit work: territorial losses among ribeirinhos and fishers, production unpredictability among farmers and colonos, urban pressures for delivery workers – all forms of anticipatory anxiety in the face of a future perceived as increasingly uninhabitable.

Ribeirinhos (riverine communities)

The *ribeirinhos* show the highest levels of sadness (**18.7%**) and despair (**9.8%**) among traditional communities. The forced displacement caused by the Belo Monte dam has produced psychological suffering experienced as a form of mourning, confirmed by interviews conducted in the RUCs, where many residents describe a daily life marked by social isolation and inactivity.

This uprooting is accompanied by a loss of cultural continuity: navigation on the Xingu River – once a vital artery – has become risky or impossible during low-water periods. Territorial disorganisation and the decline of social exchange foster a collective sense of abandonment. This distress clearly falls within the realm of solastalgia – a pain linked to territorial transformation, amplified by the ribeirinhos' direct climatic dependence and their institutional marginalisation in the post-dam context.

Indigenous peoples

High determination (**36.9%**, compared to **27.8%** among non-Indigenous respondents) contrasts with lower contentment (**41.3%**) and heightened signs of emotional distress: self-harm thoughts (1.1%, vs. 0.1%), anxiety (**7.6%**), despair (**3.3%**), and slightly higher alcohol or drug use (**1.1%**). These disparities reveal an intense psychological mobilisation, shaped by identity and territorial defence since Belo Monte, but sustained at a high emotional cost. Recent droughts have worsened agricultural losses, increasing dependence on support structures in Altamira and the incidence of risk behaviours. This “internalised struggle” illustrates the paradox of a militant resilience that preserves identity while undermining mental health under combined climatic and institutional pressures.

Gold miners' shelter. Photo credit: Jean-François Véran. CLISEVE© Altamira, 2025.

“There’s so much human activity, so much pollution, and nothing is being done. They’re always talking about deforestation, but nothing changes. You can’t improve the climate by cutting down forests. What revolts me most is what’s happening to our Indigenous lands. Yes, there are reserves, but they’re constantly being attacked by national and international companies. Now everything is a carbon project: they promise a lot of money, but in the end, nothing changes. They claim to ‘offset’ destruction by capturing carbon elsewhere, while continuing to destroy here. It’s just patchwork — they pay to protect over there while polluting even more here. They say the Amazon is the lungs of the world... but what are we really doing to save it? Every year, there’s more deforestation — and with it, more diseases linked to air and pollution.”
(Indigenous leader, 57 years old)

Colonos (settlers)

The *colonos* display the highest rate of emotional fatigue in the entire study (**45.6%**), combined with lower contentment (**39.2%**) and a very low level of organisation (**3.8%**). Anxiety remains moderate (**7.1%**), yet their chronic land-tenure insecurity reveals a diffuse exhaustion rather than acute distress. Often farmers without land titles or working on others’ plots, they have limited adaptive capacity to droughts and rising heat. Their eco-anxiety stems less from the climate itself than from the impossibility of planning for the future: they lack both irrigation means and land-title guarantees. This profile reflects a cumulative psychological fatigue, standing at the edge of breakdown.

“From 1970 to 1980, it was an easy time. There was chestnut, rubber, and fish. I worked in aquarium fishing — *olho-de-bota*, *acaré*. Back then, most people made a living from catching ornamental fish. I sold directly in Altamira. The *acaré* disappeared, because it doesn’t reproduce when everything is dry. It used to be in November and December, but now the river has dried up. We used to earn 300 reais a day; today, barely 20. Jobs here are very scarce. Since then, I’ve been a gold miner and worked with a lot of mercury. I may be contaminated, but I’m not sure. I don’t want to die under a dam — that scares me. My daughter left so she wouldn’t fall into depression.” (Community leader, 65 years old)

Interview at the Casa do Índio (a reception house in downtown Altamira for Indigenous people living in the forest). Photo credit: Charles de Souza Oliveira. CLISEVE© Altamira, 2025.

PROFESSIONAL SECTORS

Heatmap 2. Scores of Main States × Sectors (N=899) – CLISEVE© Altamira, 2025.

Sector	Happy	Determined	Tired	Anxious	Desperate
Agriculture/Livestock	61.4%	21.3%	28.1%	4.5%	1.9%
Artisanal Fishing	27.2%	39.5%	39.5%	7.0%	5.3%
Transport/Taxi/Delivery	55.6%	24.4%	31.1%	13.3%	3.3%
Gold Panning	30.6%	27.8%	41.7%	8.3%	5.6%
Specialized Services	45.8%	33.6%	29.0%	5.3%	3.1%
Construction	45.5%	33.7%	25.7%	5.0%	2.0%
Urban Cleaning (Garbage Collectors)	58.1%	30.2%	34.9%	2.3%	2.3%

Agriculture

Contentment is high (**61.3%**). Determination (**21.8%**) remains, however, limited by cumulative fatigue linked to prolonged heatwaves and the 2024 drought, which weakened the plantations. This sector retains a strong sense of identity, with the connection to living beings acting as a protective resource, but climate pressure and uncertainty about harvests generate latent stress. Several respondents link sleep disturbances or anxiety attacks to the fear of new agricultural losses. On the benches of the union’s support office, interviewed farmers readily identify the direct psychological dimension linked to the climate’s impact on family production.

Specialized services and Construction

These sectors show a contentment level of **45.8%** (services) and **45.5%** (construction), associated with determination of around **33%**. Indicators of psychological distress remain moderate (**~10%**), and fatigue (**~27%**) remains the main symptom. Employment stability acts as a protective factor, but heat and hierarchical pressure sustain latent stress.

Transport and delivery

Anxiety peaks (**13%**) are among the highest in the study, accompanied by persistent fatigue and an average satisfaction rate of **55.6%**. Drivers describe constant heat stress, worsened by fire smoke, dehydration, and traffic disruptions caused by heat and rain. The data highlight an invisible psychological distress, fueled by real-time pressure and the logic of digital applications, which translates into a form of “algorithmic paranoia” (Alacovska et. al., 2022). This combination of precarity, climatic exposure, and over-solicitation makes the transport sector one of the most psychologically vulnerable.

Gold panning

Low contentment (**30.6%**), high fatigue (**41.7%**), despair (**8.1%**), and anxiety (**8.3%**) indicate psychological distress exacerbated by climate-related accidents and the dam’s water management, which floods production sites. Mental exhaustion is compounded by social isolation and increased alcohol use, in a context of uncertainty surrounding the Belo Sun project and a complete absence of psychological support. Several recent cases of suicide among young people confirm the fragility of a population subjected to a triple exposure: climatic, chemical (mercury), and emotional.

Artisanal fishing

A strong sense of determination (**37.8%**) coexists with fatigue (**42%**) and despair (**10.9%**). Only **26.9%** report being satisfied — 2.3 times fewer than farmers. This configuration reflects a deep ecological mourning, linked to the scarcity of fish and the climatic disruption of the piracema (spawning) cycle, which undermines community reference points. Collective psychological exhaustion is rooted in territorial loss and hydrological uncertainty. Political mobilization functions as a mechanism of psychological survival, though at the cost of significant emotional strain.

Presence of the research team during a fishermen's protest at the Belo Monte dam site, as part of demands for financial compensation. Credit: Jean-François Véran. CLISEVE© Altamira, 2025.

What CLISEVE© Altamira 2025 Reveals About Mental Health

- **Outdoor work is not pathogenic in itself:** it can be a source of well-being when the connection to living environments and territory remains intact, but becomes a source of suffering when these symbolic continuities are broken (as among fishermen and ribeirinhos).
- **An “emotional grey zone” affects nearly one-fifth of workers (19.2%):** a diffuse malaise marked by fatigue, anxiety, and sleep disturbances—without tipping into acute distress, yet weighing on daily life and the ability to plan for the future.
- **A minority are in acute distress (4.4%):** 39 individuals encountered show extreme vulnerability, where climate acts as a tipping factor, underscoring the need for early detection and psychological support.

Urban cleaning / Garbage collectors

The cleaning workers of Altamira show a high level of contentment (**58.1%**) and notable determination (**30.2%**), but also fatigue (**34.9%**). Their psychological resilience relies on formal employment status (municipal or contract workers), teamwork, and fixed territorial assignments, which foster a sense of belonging. However, extreme heat and limited hierarchical autonomy generate a form of “silent saturation,” oscillating between partial recognition and daily weariness.

“Anxiety comes all the time — I take all kinds of tests and nothing shows up. I can't sleep at night, my legs feel heavy, and there are hundreds of people ahead of me waiting to see the psychiatrist.”
(street vendor, 48 years old)

“During rounds, we often feel tired when we're out in the sun for too long... We feel exhausted, but we have to keep working anyway. It's very tiring work — no fixed hours, lots of heavy lifting.” (day laborer unloading trucks, 32 years old)

“I wanted to do too many things and couldn't manage, then I went days without sleeping — I thought I was going to die.”
(motorcycle taxi driver, 31 years old)

- **Solastalgia and eco-anxiety are empirically documented:** they reflect a loss of connection to the territory and a chronic unease in the face of climatic unpredictability.
- **Health–climate risk at work does not depend on climate alone:** it amplifies social and occupational divides — land insecurity, informality, uberization — and unfolds within contexts of violence and structural inequality.
- **Community belonging is not uniformly protective:** for traditional peoples, “securing oneself” within institutional arenas represents both a resource and a psychological burden, increasing relational vulnerability.
- **The ambivalence of climate** — both suffering and resource — lies at the heart of psychological experience: ecological awareness can fuel mobilization and resistance, but at the cost of existential fatigue that reveals the limits of resilience.

CLIMATE UNDER TENSION: WHEN CLIMATIC STRAIN FUELS VIOLENCE

In Altamira, climate change does not create violence, but it intensifies its fronts: competition for water and land, land and agro-industrial pressures, urban tensions, and discrimination. By catalyzing these dynamics, it transforms exposure to violence into a direct component of health-climate risk at work.

This analysis continues the reflections developed within the CONTER project (ANR–EHSS), which examines how environmental and social configurations reshape contemporary regimes of violence.

Violence and Territories in Altamira: A Historical Continuity

From colonization to Belo Monte, violence has been a constant thread in Altamira’s development. Once known as the “capital of the Transamazonian Highway,” the city was, between 2015 and 2017, the most violent in Brazil, with a record rate of 107 homicides per 100,000 inhabitants.

The construction of the Belo Monte dam triggered a demographic and social explosion: the population tripled, accompanied by a massive influx of workers, prostitution, drug trafficking, and the establishment of criminal factions – organized groups originating from Brazil’s major prisons (e.g., Comando Vermelho and CCA).

Even today, the RUCs (Urban Collective Resettlements) concentrate diffuse forms of violence linked to evictions, climate inequalities, and institutional neglect. Within this continuum, violence remains a transversal reality, reactivated with each cycle of growth, drought, or resettlement.

! A homicide rate of 107 per 100,000 inhabitants in 2017: during the construction of the Belo Monte dam, Altamira was considered the most violent municipality in Brazil.

(Atlas da Violência 2019, IPEA / Fórum Brasileiro de Segurança Pública).

Historical timeline. Violence, territory and Climate. CLISEVE@ Altamira, 2025.

! Nearly one in two workers (49.4%) report having experienced some form of violence over the past two years – a structural tension exacerbated by climate crises.

Figure 13. Distribution of Reported Forms of Violence (N=899) – CLISEVE@ Altamira, 2025.

Violence and Climate: Three Regimes in Altamira

The study identifies three regimes of violence, which the local climate both amplifies and displaces (see Graph 13 and Heatmap 3):

Systemic territorial (gold miners, fishers)

Low water levels, droughts, and the depletion of fish stocks reduce available resources, exacerbating threats (**56.1%**) and forced displacements (up to **13.9%**). On Ilha da Fazenda, the garimpeiros (artisanal gold miners) are subjected to a deliberate strategy of intimidation: *“It’s a goldfield in its cruelest form, where everything is expensive and violence keeps growing.”* Among fishers, **45.6%** report explicit threats of losing access to fishing zones, and **18.5%** report damage to their equipment. *“The landowner arrived with his armed capangas,”* one of them recounts. Between the artificial floods caused by the dam and the Xingu’s recurring droughts, hydrological instability sustains a climate of fear and ecological mourning: *“Today, everything is gone. Our survival no longer exists.”*

Structural land-based (agriculture)

Prolonged droughts and slash-and-burn practices weaken harvests, reducing income and heightening local tensions. Climate irregularities further amplify these conflicts, with **31.8%** of farmers reporting land-related violence, **17%** direct threats, and **22%** disputes over land ownership. Nearly **one in ten** denounces a denial of rights through the non-registration or refusal to validate their property titles. Here, the climate acts as a catalyst: each dry season rekindles the fear of being dispossessed — either through the inability to maintain one’s land or through land grabbing by others.

Cumulative urban (transport, street, services)

Extreme heat, torrential rains, and environmental stress exacerbate tensions in an already saturated public space. Urban transport workers face **38%** verbal violence, **15%** moral harassment, and **12%** thefts or property damage. In the streets, street vendors report **22.8%** verbal violence, **16.8%** discrimination, and **20.8%** material losses. Under the effects of the climate, these aggressions multiply: heat, long queues, and delays increase irritability and conflict, turning everyday violence into an integral component of the health-climate risk associated with urban work.

“The fishers of the Xingu call for help to COP 30”: a message of despair. Credit: Jean-François V éran. CLISEVE© Altamira, 2025.

“*The landowner arrived and ordered us to leave the place where we were. We had just arrived and made a small fire to grill a fish before going back to fishing. He said he didn’t want anyone there because the land belonged to him, and he came arrogantly, accompanied by armed guards. We just told him we would cook the fish there, and he replied that we had no right to do so and had to leave immediately. So we put out the fire, packed our things, loaded everything back into the boat, and had to leave under threat.*”
(Fisher, 54 years old)

“*He’ll end up being expelled, one way or another. (...) Either he moves to the outskirts of the city, crowded in with everyone else, or he goes even farther, to the areas where there’s still a bit of forest — and there, he ends up clearing it, he has no choice. (...) Others will seize that land to resell it. And he’ll end up being expelled again.*”
(Farmer, 35 years old)

Heatmap 3. Distribution of types of violence by sector (N=899) – CLISEVE© Altamira, 2025.

Violence and Eco-Anxiety: A Chain Reaction

Each additional exposure to violence increases psychological distress (+0.10). Multiple exposures combine fatigue, anxiety, and despair, amplified by a diffuse eco-anxiety: climate and social insecurity intertwine to produce cumulative psychological strain.

The study highlighted the interplay between climate and violence in outdoor urban work. Credit: Jean-François Véran. CLISEVE© Altamira, 2025.

What CLISEVE© Altamira Reveals About the Relationship Between Violence and Climate:

Exposure to violence is, in itself, a health-climate risk factor at work in Altamira:

- First, as demonstrated by the *Population Assessment Tool* applied for Médecins Sans Frontières – from which the CLISEVE© study partly originates (Véran, 2020) – both climate and violence affect physical and mental health. Violence and climate are therefore two intertwined factors whose combination heightens health-climate risk at work.
- Second, climate-related violence – whether in conflicts over water access (cases of water theft were reported during the 2024 drought) or outbursts of aggression on construction sites and in traffic when the heat becomes unbearable – builds upon structural violence surrounding access to land, water, and the city. Climate thus reinforces pre-existing structural forms of violence.
- Finally, these forms of climate-linked violence feed back into latent eco-anxiety, reactivating fear, tension, and psychological exhaustion. The study therefore demonstrates how violence and climate mutually amplify each other, creating complex health risks.

ABANDON OF ACTIVITY: THE 'RED FLAG' OF CLIMATE RESILIENCE

In Altamira, 34.7% of outdoor workers say they are considering leaving – or are certain they will leave – their occupation within the next five years. This is not a series of individual failures: it is the ultimate warning sign of cumulative climatic and social exposures, when “holding on” is no longer enough.

Figure 14. Main Indicators of the Intention to Leave One's Occupation (N=899) – CLISEVE@ Altamira, 2025

Intentions to Leave by Sector

As shown in Figure 15, the differences between sectors are striking. In transport and delivery, more than one in two workers are considering leaving their occupation (27% “possible,” 24.7% “certain”), while in urban cleaning, nearly three in ten say they intend to quit (30.2% “certain”). In contrast, artisanal fishing shows strong stability (55.8% “certain to continue”), and agriculture reflects the same rootedness, with 65.7% of respondents planning to maintain their activity despite climatic constraints.

In Altamira, urban occupations concentrate most of the intentions to leave – a sign of the social fatigue already identified in the mental health symptoms, and likely of the greater professional mobility opportunities offered by the urban environment.

Traditional occupations – fishing and agriculture – show greater resilience, expressing both a strong territorial attachment and economic dependence on local resources. This persistence illustrates how solastalgia (distress in the face of environmental degradation) can paradoxically fuel the will to stay and resist.

Figure 15. Distribution of responses to the intention to quit by sector of activity (N=899) – CLISEVE@ Altamira, 2025.

What Drives People to Leave: Psychological Distress First, Heat Second

Psychological strain – the silent engine of disengagement. The decision to leave one’s job is first and foremost rooted in psychological exhaustion, before any other indicator. Four signals weigh heavily: the feeling of threat (+0.93), family failure (+0.75), constant fatigue (+0.42), and sadness (+0.33). Each significantly increases the likelihood of wanting to quit. Overall, the lower the emotional score (imbalance between positive and negative emotions), the higher the intention to leave ($r = -0.21$; $p < 0.001$).

Extreme heat – a true physical limit. 61.5% of workers consider that beyond a certain threshold, stopping work becomes legitimate. It is therefore not just a choice but a constraint imposed by the body. The data confirm this: the more unbearable the heat is perceived to be, the higher the intention to leave one’s occupation ($r = 0.319$; $p < 0.001$).

Younger workers (<45 years old) are more likely to foresee leaving their jobs ($r = -0.11$; $p = 0.0007$), except in traditional sectors such as agriculture and fishing.

- ❗ 61.5% believe that beyond a certain heat threshold, working should be optional.
- ❗ A clear majority (62%) believe that work should stop when temperatures reach between 30 and 35 degrees Celsius.

Figure 16. Distribution of responses to the question: "From what temperature should work become optional?" (N=899) – CLISEVE© Altamira, 2025.

Collective Threshold: 30–35°C

Figure 16 illustrates the collective perception of heat thresholds beyond which work should become optional. In Altamira, most respondents place this threshold between 30°C and 35°C (26% and 36%, respectively), confirming the existence of a shared bodily and social limit. One quarter (25%) set it at 40°C, while 14% say work should never be suspended.

Younger workers are more likely to call for stopping work as early as 30–35°C ($p < 0.001$). The "Never" response is most common among 45–64-year-olds in transport, street work, gold mining, and agriculture – suggesting not so much adherence to the idea of limitless labor as a constrained acceptance due to lack of alternatives.

The same CLISEVE© study, conducted in 2024 in the French viticulture sector, shows a very similar distribution: 67.4% within the 30–35°C range (30.9% for 30°C, 36.5% for 35°C, and 32.6% for 40°C), but with no "Never" responses. This similarity suggests the existence of a broadly shared benchmark around 30–35°C, transcending social and geographical contexts.

What CLISEVE© Altamira Reveals About the Link Between Climate and Withdrawal from Work:

- In Altamira, leaving one’s occupation can be triggered by reaching a breaking point in the face of health–climate risk at work.
- This rupture emerges at the intersection of three thresholds: psychological fatigue, thermal constraint, and socio-economic pressure that prevents lasting adaptation.
- Confronted with this limit, a majority of workers agree on the need to regulate labor according to health–climate risks caused by extreme heat: more than one in two consider it legitimate to stop working between 30°C and 35°C.
- This consensus expresses a clear call for public regulation – to be integrated into risk-management plans – so that health protection no longer depends solely on individual endurance.

FROM COMMON SENSE TO CALLS FOR ACTION: A HEALTH AWARENESS FACING THE CLIMATE

In Altamira, field observations reveal a clear understanding of the basic conditions needed to protect health while working in extreme heat: drinking water, shelter, appropriate pacing, and suitable clothing.

Figure 17 highlights a set of converging needs – access to drinking water (**73.1%**), shaded areas (**49.3%**), appropriate clothing (**50.5%**), and adjusted work schedules (**48.9%**) – all considered essential by workers for climate adaptation. Yet these priorities remain unevenly implemented: only **50.6%** report having access to drinking water, **31.8%** benefit from adjusted hours, and around **46%** have suitable clothing.

The gap between expressed needs and actual conditions underscores the decisive role of institutions in regulating time, infrastructure, and supply. This transition from common sense to the identification of unmet vital needs marks the emergence of a health consciousness – one that seeks to transform basic necessities into claimed rights in response to health–climate risks at work.

“In the Heart of the Amazon, Workers Lack Water...”

The paradox is striking: in the heart of the Amazon – home to the planet’s largest reserve of freshwater – access to drinking water remains one of the most significant deficits for workers.

The study shows that this shortage is structural and worsened by recurring droughts. The operation of the Belo Monte dam has profoundly altered the hydrological regime of the Xingu River, reducing flow levels and drying up entire river branches. Added to this are the contamination of wells by mercury and pesticides, dependence on water trucks, and the challenges of sustainable municipal management of the water network installed by Norte Energia, the company operating the dam.

When the new pipelines were installed, individual artesian wells were closed by decree for sanitary reasons, increasing dependence on a collective network that remains incomplete and frequently unreliable. Successive droughts have intensified water stress across the population. At the height of the 2024 drought, access to drinking water became the central demand of social movements – a symbol of a vital right still not guaranteed.

Figure 17. Gap Between Perceived and Effectively Met Needs for Heat Adaptation (N=899) – CLISEVE@ Altamira, 2025.

“The water runs through the community, but many houses aren’t connected to the system. (...) In the RUCs, we depend on water trucks, but the water isn’t good. (...) The children often have stomach aches, and we can’t drink the river water anymore.”
(Ribeirinho worker living in a RUC, 37 years old)

“The water tastes like rust, it has an oily film. It leaves a bad taste. (...) The water has changed since Belo Monte, but no one has compensated us. Maybe it’s contaminated – we just don’t know.”
(Gold miner, 41 years old)

“Before, I had the river right in front of my house; now I have to wait for the truck. (...) Sometimes it doesn’t come, so we buy bottled water. (...) We live eight kilometers from the Xingu, and we have no water anymore.”
(Woman, 28 years old, relocated to a RUC)

Adaptation Practices and Material Constraints

In a context of limited resources, adaptation relies primarily on the most accessible solutions (Table 5). The use of personal protective equipment (**59.1%**), hydration breaks, and appropriate clothing (**~50%**) constitute the first self-protection strategies. These body-centered responses are immediate and effective, but their impact remains limited. On construction sites, in the streets, or along the Xingu River, workers improvise: soaking their shirts in water, taking refuge under a truck, stretching a plastic tarp for shade, or sharing a bottle among colleagues. In rural areas, farmers start their day earlier, before noon; in the city, cleaning workers continue without the autonomy to manage their exposure to heat. These everyday gestures reveal a form of constrained ingenuity – resilience based more on improvisation than on institutional prevention.

Conversely, more advanced technical solutions – ventilation (**17.3%**), irrigation (**23.9%**), mobile applications (**10.4%**), thermal sensors (**8.5%**) – remain out of reach, dependent on fragile infrastructure, unstable power supply, and insufficient institutional support. Adaptation thus takes shape within a tension between local initiative and structural deficiency.

Forms of adaptation vary by profession: construction workers rely on personal equipment (**78%**), farmers on irrigation (**39%**), and fishers on financial support (**81%**). Street vendors focus on water access (**63%**), while service workers tend to use digital tools (**17%**). These sector-specific analyses are detailed in the CLISEVE© occupational profiles, disseminated during local participatory feedback sessions, outside the scope of this summary report.

! Health–climate risk at work is managed primarily through self-protection gestures, which were not sufficient to prevent the multiple symptoms observed during the 2024 drought. Targeted institutional prevention could strengthen the adaptation measures already present in the field.

Table 5. Hierarchy of Adaptation Solutions According to Their Accessibility and Perceived Impact (N=899). CLISEVE© Altamira, 2025.

Immediate solutions (adaptable, inexpensive)	Conditional solutions (infrastructure, investments, access to rights)
Protective equipment – 59.1%	Ventilation/air conditioning – 17.3%
Daily activities (shade, clothing, breaks, water) ≈ 50%	Mobile applications – 10.4%
	Sensors – 8.5%
	Irrigation (all sectors) – 15.6% / 23.9% in agriculture
	Social support / health – 30.7%

“They have Starlink but no water.” (Union representative, 58 years old)

“We’ll only plant with irrigation, but there’s no project.” (Farmer, 48 years old)

“Plant more trees, put a parasol on your bike. [...] What helps against the heat is taking a dip in the river.” (Street vendor, 32 years old)

Banks of the Xingu River. Protective strategies against heat are most often basic. Credit: Jean-François Véran. CLISEVE© Altamira, 2025.

Practical Knowledge, Medical Expertise, and Data: A Triple Demand

Three main dimensions emerge from the expressed information needs (Figure 18). First, operational know-how – **42%** of respondents seek basic training on heat prevention and **47.8%** want information on suitable clothing and equipment – reflecting an immediate search for autonomy in managing bodily risk.

Second, an openness to specialized medical expertise (**30.5%**) shows that workers now recognize the effects of climate as a matter of health, calling for professional guidance to interpret and address physical impacts. Finally, the demand for validated scientific data (**23.6%**) expresses a desire to understand and legitimize these experiences through objective references capable of supporting claims and collective decision-making.

These expectations do not stem from increased dependency on institutions but from a willingness to articulate different regimes of knowledge: lived experience, technical competence, and scientific evidence. They signal the emergence of a space of co-production between public health, occupational medicine, and climatology – where knowledge becomes a tool for negotiation, self-protection, social recognition, and institutional dialogue.

 42,2 % of workers want preventive training on health–climate risks, but only 24% have received it.

Sharp Inequalities in Climate Prevention

Formal employees benefit from **51%** training coverage and **43.8%** action plans, compared with only **18.9%** and **13.7%** for informal workers, and less than 10% for the self-employed. Cleaning agents (**46.5%**) and construction workers (**28.7%**) appear better covered, though mainly through traditional safety programs that do not yet integrate climate considerations. This divide highlights the need for differentiated support and field-based mechanisms. In transport-related jobs, risk assessment (**20.7%**) and information tools such as smartphone apps are priorities; in agriculture, the strong demand for combined support (**65%**) underscores the urgency of preventive measures adapted to climatic realities.

Figure 18. Main indicators of information demand (N=899). CLISEVE© Altamira, 2025.

 “There has been no information at all about respiratory symptoms related to smoke or heat, and environmental monitoring doesn’t take this into account.”
(Epidemiologist, Altamira)

 “Climate change is little studied; programs are starting to include it, but coverage remains patchy.”
(Professor, Altamira)

Climate Risk: Absent from Prevention Frameworks

The gap between workers’ expectations and existing measures reveals a clear deficit: **42.2%** of workers want preventive training, but only **24%** have received it. Likewise, barely **27%** report any specific actions against heat, while **48%** observe none at all. These figures reflect the lack of integration of health–climate risk at work into Brazilian regulatory frameworks (NR-1, PGR), which remain focused on conventional occupational hazards.

● The CLISEVE© platform aims to help bridge this gap by offering training and support modules dedicated to health–climate risk in the workplace.

Figure 19. Identified Obstacles and Supports for Adaptation to Health–Climate Risk at Work (N=899). CLISEVE© Altamira, 2025.

“It’s been 36 years since my father settled here. Only last year did he finally get his land document. He spent 35 years without one. And today, my father is the exception of exceptions. Because the vast majority of these family farmers have no property title. Without documents, they can’t access credit or any of the other programs that would allow them to technically improve their systems in the face of climate change.”
(Farmer, 45 years old)

Levers to Activate: Costs, Land Tenure, and Support

This section highlights three decisive levers of adaptation – cost, land tenure, and technical support – which shape both perceived obstacles and possible margins of action in addressing health–climate risk at work (Figure 19).

Cost: A Structural Barrier (42.4%)

Costs are the most frequently cited obstacle (42.4%); in agriculture, this rises to 54.2%, alongside strong calls for financial support (71.2%) and targeted needs (irrigation 39.1%; equipment 62.7%). For street vendors, resilience depends on access to climate microcredit (coolers, shelters, PPE), confirming that while “the gestures” are known, they remain out of reach. Among ribeirinhos, the occasional cost of transporting water for several hours by boat illustrates the economic dead end during drought periods.

Land Tenure and Administrative Access: A Difficult Path (14.7%)

Regularizing land, obtaining a CPF (tax identification number), registering as an individual micro-entrepreneur (MEI), or proving residence are often unachievable steps for mobile rural families. Agricultural subsidies, climate aid, and inclusion in municipal plans all require extensive documentation: proof of residence, CPF, land regularization, NIS, CadÚnico registration, and plot number. Here, bureaucratic compliance becomes a prerequisite for climate–health adaptation.

Technical Support – Adaptation on Hold (26.8%)

Technical support is requested by 26.8% of respondents (41% in agriculture). Expectations focus on simple measures: shaded areas (59%), adjusted work hours (54.6%), and water points (78.2% in construction). The gap between demand and implementation – particularly visible in construction (55.4% vs. 27.7%) – reflects an organizational barrier rather than a lack of know-how. In agriculture and fishing, technical priorities involve practical water management, equipment maintenance, and exposure-time planning, while in street vending, needs relate to portable shade and hydration solutions. Overall, this points to a demand for pragmatic support, targeting the material and organizational conditions of adaptation rather than new knowledge.

Among street vendors, 17.4% report not needing any support. This apparent lack of demand likely does not indicate real self-sufficiency, but rather the difficulty – typical of this precarious segment – in formulating concrete requests for assistance.

- These results confirm that adapting to health–climate risk at work faces the challenge of transforming available information and knowledge into concrete means of action. The study shows that workers clearly identify what needs to be done – protecting themselves, obtaining equipment, organizing work – but that action remains constrained by three structural factors: cost, administrative access, and effective technical support.

ALTAMIRA AND THE SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT GOALS OF COP30

In the final section of the CLISEVE© survey, two questions helped link the perception of rights to that of public policies: **1-** “Among the following rights, which would you say you actually have access to?” **2-** “Among the following measures, which would you say your city implements?”

This dual approach aims to assess both the real access to vital rights (water, health, food, equality, energy, sanitation) and the visibility of municipal policies meant to guarantee them. It allows us to observe whether residents perceive a coherent chain between local policies and living conditions.

This local diagnosis fits fully within the perspective of COP30, where the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) 6 (Water), 8 (Decent Work), 10 (Reduced Inequalities), 11 (Sustainable Cities), and 13 (Climate Action) converge.

The “rights pyramid” (Figure 21) reveals a solid yet incomplete foundation: food (**74.9%**), health (**73.2%**), and water (**68.9%**) cover the majority of outdoor workers, while sanitation (**43.5%**) and gender equality (**25.1%**) concentrate the main exclusions. Workers connected to urban networks – in cleaning, construction, and services – enjoy better access than fishers and garimpeiros (gold miners). “Access to water” remains domestic; at work, it is irregular and depends on individual initiative. Women, more often residing in RUCs as part of their activities, face cumulative deprivation – lack of water, domestic burden, and isolation. For ribeirinhos and Indigenous peoples, drought and water contamination amount to a true violence of water.

Altamira is a city where vital rights have advanced, but network and equality rights remain fragile – especially in light of the challenges of climate adaptation.

Figure 20. Mirror Pyramid of Declared Rights (No Access on the Left, Access on the Right) (N=899). CLISEVE© Altamira, 2025.

Convergences – Productive Alignments

Certain alignments observed indicate a strong perceived coherence between local policies and Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) recognized as effective rights.

Food ↔ Sustainable Agriculture (SDGs 2 and 12)

In agriculture, **71.4%** of respondents perceive municipal measures related to local or sustainable production, and nearly two-thirds (**64.9%**) report good access to food. This correspondence suggests a tangible link between agricultural policies and food security – where sustainability becomes a concrete vehicle for the right to nourishment.

Health ↔ Fight Against Poverty and Inequality (SDGs 3 and 10)

Among formal employees – in specialized services, cleaning, and construction – more than **60%** identify both social measures (employment, poverty reduction) and effective access to health care (**73.2%** across the sample). Here, the social component of municipal action emerges as a key determinant in addressing health–climate risk at work, as it strengthens prevention and adaptation capacities.

These convergences show that the articulation between social and environmental policies reinforces collective resilience – a central issue in the Belém debates and a marker of the coherence expected between SDGs 3, 6, 10, and 13.

Water, Work, and Equality: The Challenges of a Just Transition

Alongside the observed alignments, clear gaps emerge between certain experienced rights and perceived public measures.

Water and Conservation – SDGs 6 and 15

Drinking water, reported as accessible by **68.9%** of respondents, is only weakly associated with conservation policies (**20%–22%**). In other words, those who have water do not connect it to environmental policy, and those who perceive conservation actions do not see them as ensuring real access to water. Ecological sustainability remains detached from urban equity: protecting water as a resource does not guarantee its distribution or quality of use.

Work, Energy, and Production – SDGs 7, 8, and 12

Similarly, energy and decent work are linked more to social measures (**40%–45%**) than to sustainable production policies, revealing a gap between environmental action and the local economy. Residents associate these areas more with poverty reduction or job creation than with energy transition or productive innovation – showing that sustainability policies remain largely invisible in the everyday realities of work.

Gender Equality – SDGs 5 and 10

Finally, gender equality – the most fragile right (**25.1%** access) – paradoxically shows the strongest connection to municipal measures (**>25%** across most categories): actions are visible (notably through social movement activism) but their effects remain limited. This visibility without effectiveness fuels a sense of dissonance and social fatigue, especially in peripheral neighborhoods and RUCs.

- The convergences between experienced rights and local policies embody the social foundations of climate adaptation – evidence that SDG coherence becomes perceptible when measures are tangible.
- The dissonances, meanwhile, reveal the missing links of a just transition: water, equality, and effective access to services remain the blind spots of climate justice.
- Urban health–climate risk emerges precisely from this gap between proclaimed sustainability and lived rights. The study turns it into a lever for dialogue – connecting local evidence, public monitoring, and international commitments, from the municipality to COP30.

“*The real violence is the lack of water. There’s no point in mobilizing without denouncing this violence – the violence of thirst. We are crying out for water. We have to wait until four in the afternoon just to get a bucket. A million-real well produced nothing – the pump rusted. We are calling for help.*”
(Social movement activist)

“*The problem with women is that they don’t present themselves as farmers. We explain to them that anyone who lives in the countryside is a farmer. When they register to vote, they declare themselves as housewives, but we encourage them to identify as farmers. In most cases, it’s the man who is recognized as the one working in agriculture.*” (Union representative)

“Altamira, City of Work”. This inscription on a downtown roundabout encapsulates a collective identity built on effort and production.

Recognizing the health–climate risk faced by outdoor workers means extending that identity into a policy of protection and acknowledgment of real labor – precisely what CLISEVE© seeks to promote. Credit: Jean-François Véran. *CLISEVE© Altamira, 2025.*

Presentation on health–climate risk at work by the research team at the **Belo Monte Municipal School – Vila Belo Monte**. Credit: Jean-François Véran. *CLISEVE© Altamira, 2025.*

Presentation on health–climate risk at work within an **industrial maintenance and operations company**.

Objective: to integrate the health–climate dimension into the existing Risk Management Plan. Credit: Jean-François Véran. *CLISEVE© Altamira, 2025.*

FIVE KEY ACTIONS TO ADDRESS HEALTH-CLIMATE RISK IN ALTAMIRA

The CLISEVE® Altamira study revealed a shared understanding, exposure, and experience of climate among workers, institutions, and residents – who now speak a common language of risk.

These points of convergence define the foundations of a community of action capable of responding collectively to climate challenges, built around five complementary levers: a municipal campaign, social mediation, mental health support, a 90-day corporate engagement plan, and CLISEVE® certification.

ACTION SHEET 1 – CLISEVE® MUNICIPAL CAMPAIGN

● Objective:

Make Altamira a pioneer city in health–climate risk prevention, based on identified needs: 42.2% of respondents request simple training on heat exposure, 47.8% want information on suitable protective equipment, and 30.5% seek health information related to climate risk. Observations from unions, associations, and local health units (UBS) show a lack of climate awareness, even though heat-related symptoms (headaches, dizziness, dehydration) are frequent.

● Key Actions:

Participatory CLISEVE® workshops bringing together health agents, teachers, and associations (UBS, CRAS, CREAS) to discuss local data and collective solutions.

- Mobile training sessions held in professional groups, schools, and municipal companies, integrated into existing campaigns (dengue, STI prevention, occupational safety).
- Mobilization of UBS, schools, and community radios to disseminate key information: heat thresholds, rest breaks, hydration, and first aid.
- Support from CEREST to adapt materials to the most exposed professions (construction, transport, street vending).

● Expected Impact:

- Transition from fragmented information to an integrated prevention framework, measurable through:
- Participation rates above 60% of schools and UBS within 12 months;
 - Inclusion of health–climate indicators in municipal plans (PPA, PGR);
 - A measurable reduction in reported heat-related symptoms during extreme heat periods (baseline: 68% in 2025).

ACTION SHEET 2 – SOCIAL MEDIATION

● Objective:

Reduce health–climate risk at work linked to lack of access to essential rights – water, equipment, protection, and health – through the resolution of identified administrative barriers.

Data from CLISEVE® Altamira 2025 show that 30.9% of workers request information about available aid, and 14.7% report land regularization issues or difficulties obtaining micro-entrepreneur (MEI) status, which prevent them from accessing adaptation measures (purchase of PPE, water storage, adjusted work hours).

● Key Actions:

- Mobile “health–climate” support desks in high-exposure workplaces (construction sites, markets, rural zones), providing assistance with document regularization required to access climate aid, adaptation credits, and preventive equipment.
- Targeted accompaniment by Community Health Agents (ASC) to identify cases where missing document documents directly compromise heat prevention (access to water, healthcare, or protective equipment).
- Municipal emergency protocols: simplified procedures for immediate access to essential measures (water distribution, PPE, collective shelters) before full administrative completion.
- Inter-institutional monitoring (CEREST, SEMSA, CRAS) to ensure continuity between social mediation and occupational health–climate prevention.

● Expected Impact:

- CLISEVE® Mediation Desk (one-stop hub) – CRAS/CREAS/UBS/Trade Unions. Screening, guidance, and referral using a social-climate record.
- Document regularization (CPF, NIS, digital work card, MEI, land title/INCRA, when applicable).
- Effective access to services (UBS/ CAPS/ CRAS/ CREAS/ Civil Defense).
- Risk communication and guidance (help desks / discussion circles).

The *ambulancha* – a river health and mediation unit – illustrates the key role of service mobility in reducing health–climate risk at work and embodies the spirit of CLISEVE® social mediation: bringing rights, water, and prevention closer to those most exposed. Credit: Jean-François Vêran. CLISEVE® Altamira, 2025.

ACTION SHEET 3 – MENTAL HEALTH AND CLIMATE

● Objective:

Address the rise in psychological symptoms linked to climate conditions – stress, anxiety, sleep disorders, chronic fatigue – observed in over half of CLISEVE© Altamira respondents. Field research confirmed that extreme heat, displacement, and loss of crops or housing generate emotional exhaustion that is often unrecognized, hindered by stigma and lack of accessible services.

● Key Actions:

- Develop and test a “Climate and Eco-Anxiety at Work” protocol in UBS and CAPS units, based on CLISEVE© Altamira indicators (perceived temperatures, symptoms, alert behaviors).
- Establish discussion groups on climate vulnerability, led by Community Health Agents (ACS), integrating worker testimonies about daily adaptation to heat.
- Produce local participatory studies on eco-anxiety and climate perceptions to support public policies with context-based psychological indicators.
- Integrate mental health prevention into professional and municipal heat-awareness trainings to recognize signs of exhaustion before decompensation occurs.

● Expected Impact:

- Creation of a local reference framework on the psychological effects of climate, recognized by UBS–CAPS–RAPS networks.
- Increase in early detection of heat-related stress symptoms (target: +40% within 12 months).
- Emergence of a climate–mental health culture linking psychological well-being with real working conditions.

ACTION SHEET 4 – 90-DAY CORPORATE INITIATIVE

● Objective:

Integrate health–climate risk management into the daily operations of companies. Data from CLISEVE© Altamira show that 78.2% of construction workers report a lack of water points, 59% a lack of shaded areas, and 54.6% wish for adjusted work schedules. Despite this awareness, only 27.7% state that concrete measures have been implemented. The challenge is therefore organizational: turning awareness into verifiable adaptation.

● Key Actions:

- Launch a participatory health–climate workshop per work team (≤ 3 hours) to identify the three most feasible short-term actions.
- Implement a health–climate risk management plan with written commitments (who does what, by when), followed by progress reviews at 30, 60, and 90 days.
- Install a monthly mini-monitoring system using CLISEVE© indicators.
- Integrate collected data into the existing PGR (Risk Management Plan) to connect occupational safety with climate prevention.

● Expected Impact:

- Within three months, a measurable reduction in symptoms related to health–climate risk among participating teams.
- Fewer work interruptions on days of extreme heat. Early CLISEVE© pilot programs demonstrate that this 90-day model turns commitments into observable results while improving worker satisfaction and retention.

A researcher speaks with a resident during a home visit – illustrating the active identification of situations of psychological distress, a central principle of the study: reaching out to people where the effects of climate on mental health first appear. Credit: Charles de Souza Oliveira. CLISEVE© Altamira, 2025.

ACTION SHEET 5 – CLISEVE® CERTIFICATION FOR HEALTH-CLIMATE RISK AT WORK MANAGEMENT

● Objective:

Highlight and reward companies and institutions that translate health-climate risk prevention at work into concrete practices.

Data from CLISEVE® Altamira reveal a marked gap between risk perception (64.4%) and the actual implementation of measures. The certification recognizes those that take effective action.

● Key Actions:

- Develop the CLISEVE® Workplace Health-Climate Framework, with field-validated indicators.
- Implement a two-step process: engagement (90 days), certification (12 months).
- Publish an annual public dashboard on workplace health-climate risk management, ensuring transparency and encouraging healthy competition among actors.

● Expected Impact:

- Creation of a recognized local standard for workplace health-climate risk management, measurable through: An increase in the number of certified teams (target: ≥ 60% in the first year).
- A reduction in incidents and symptoms related to health-climate risk in certified sites.
- Recognition of CLISEVE® certification as a governance tool for health-climate risk, linking prevention, productivity, and climate transition.

Presentation of the study, sheltered from the sun during a crossing of the Xingu River. Credit: Jean-François Véran. CLISEVE® Altamira, 2025.

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GENERAL CONCLUSION

From a Community of Experience to a Community of Action

The CLISEVE© Altamira study first demonstrates that outdoor work is the common denominator of climate exposure and, as such, the foundation of a shared community of perception and experience. This interpretive key runs throughout the report. It does not erase sectoral differences (exposure contexts, tools, work intensity, employment status) or disparities in vulnerability, but it situates them within a shared framework — that of outdoor labor. From this community of exposure and perception can emerge a community of action. Our strategy of developing CLISEVE© as a platform follows this logic: upon publication of this report, the CLISEVE© team will initiate local restitution workshops and propose concrete actions to help transform shared experience into collective capacity for action.

Health–Climate Risk at Work: A Concept Oriented Toward Decision-Making and Implementation

The second contribution lies in the relevance of the concept of health–climate risk at work. CLISEVE© does not treat perception as a “subjective supplement” to meteorological data or biomedical thresholds. Lived experience is part of the phenomenon itself: it reveals situated indicators that escape conventional observation systems — physical and psychological symptoms, constraints on tools, mobility and rhythms, ruptures in professional continuity, loss of productivity, task efficiency and meaning, and the weakening of supply and storage chains.

Health–climate risk at work is not merely endured; it generates dynamics — hesitation, withdrawal, misunderstanding, maladaptation, risk-taking, but also organizational innovation, resilience, and emerging opportunities. In Altamira, decisive “innovation” is not primarily technological: it lies in the synergy of practical know-how and the craftsmanship already mobilized by workers, and in the ability to elevate these into collective dynamics — transforming them into technically supported, better-funded, and coordinated levers for action.

Certain modes of action — such as work reorganization, structured mutual aid, or replication of best practices — are low-cost and often rapidly effective.

“The real violence is the lack of water”

Within this framework, water holds an emblematic place. The fact that access to drinking water at workplaces emerges as the foremost concern is not a moral reminder of “basic needs,” but rather a precise indicator of health–climate risk at work as it is experienced through physical effort. In the Amazon — the heart of the planet’s largest freshwater basin — the water scarcity experienced in Altamira is a well-known warning sign, but one that this study makes measurable through its own indicators. Symptoms of dehydration, always involving suffering and sometimes leading to serious medical conditions, echo the 2024 municipal decrees of hydric stress at the institutional level. The study’s lens thus clarifies a public paradox: it is precisely where water is most “present” that its human accessibility in the workplace becomes critical. If it was already known that infrastructure, governance, and organization outweigh mere physical availability, then it is time to draw all the consequences of this fact with regard to water access and health–climate risk at work.

Preventing Health–Climate Risk at Work Requires Formal Recognition of Work Frameworks

The study acknowledges its limits. Its focus on work leaves outside its scope a large share of daily activities — domestic, caregiving, and that continuum between home and professional space that structures so many lives. Yet these activities also entail significant exposure to health–climate risk. In the field, we observed union and community mobilizations aimed at formalizing autonomous or informal activities (fishing, agriculture, street vending). Our results support them: the formalization of work, even at the level of micro-entrepreneurship, is not merely an administrative status — it is a protective framework that embeds individuals within collective mechanisms for risk management (access to prevention, information, action plans, equipment, and rights).

From Conflict to Coherence: Organizing Through Health–Climate Risk at Work

The Altamira region faces a cumulative effect: megaprojects (such as Belo Monte) and climate impacts reinforce one another. The CLISEVE© framework sheds light on this dynamic without diluting responsibility: one must avoid “blaming everything on climate” when infrastructure and urban planning (water, shade, ventilation), labor regulation (schedules, hydration breaks, PPE), and governance (oversight, standards, alerts) depend on decisions made at local, regional, national, and both private and public levels.

From this perspective, managing health–climate risk at work becomes a productive organizing principle: the emergence of a powerful, external, and shared factor forces the overcoming of blockages and the reconfiguration of conflict lines. Addressing it within a company or institution means reordering responsibilities within a consensual framework: climate may not be attributable to any one actor, but every organization is responsible for how it manages health–climate risk at work — through its schedules, facilities, procedures, and control mechanisms. The health–climate risk framework thus serves as an architecture of coherence: it clarifies who must do what, when, and with what means, aligning the operational obligations of public and private actors toward a shared objective.

Traditional Communities: Work as a Common Framework

This approach also casts new light on *ribeirinho* and Indigenous communities. It first calls for recognizing the specificity of a form of work that is coextensive with a way of life — a specificity made all the more crucial as the legal recognition of traditional communities provides them with tools of defense against powerful economic, speculative, and political pressures. The ongoing controversies around extractive projects such as the Belo Sun gold mine are clear examples: protecting these communities also means defending the broader interests of all affected populations.

At the same time, the CLISEVE© lens — centered on health–climate risk at work — makes visible dimensions that would remain less perceptible through a purely identity-based approach. It creates new synergies with cross-sectoral professional frameworks — water, health, mobility, and the organization of time and workspace — bridging environmental justice and occupational well-being.

Facing Health–Climate Risk: Work as a Framework for Belonging and Organization

Work, as a shared framework, allows communities to combine resources and strengthen internal capacities by linking them to collective systems of prevention, equipment, and rights.

Ultimately, after this journey, we hope the concept of health–climate risk at work has fulfilled its dual promise — of analysis and action.

Analytical, because it connects climate, health, and work organization; documents multiple exposures (environmental hazards, occupational constraints, social determinants); and provides a comparative language across professions, seasons, and territories. Action-oriented, because it guides decision-making: officially recognizing health–climate risk within occupational health (alongside NR-1 and PGR), ensuring access to preventive training and action plans — including for informal and self-employed workers — and mobilizing the public health system together with national health and safety networks, companies, and organizations to equip and empower work collectives.

The contribution of the *CLISEVE© Altamira 2025* study lies here, we hope: to make visible a shared community of exposure beyond fragmented sectors; to objectify lived indicators too long dismissed as “subjective feelings”; to describe mechanisms of multiple exposure; and to anchor collective solutions in the concrete realities of work.

Timeline and Access to Documents

The presentation of results within the UN-Habitat *Circuito Urbano* (October 2025) marked a first step. The upcoming restitution workshops in Altamira will be the second. On this occasion, detailed sectoral briefs will be available upon request (jean-francois.veran@lapa-research.com). The full scientific report is also available for consultation. These documents are meant to be shared and mobilized — we invite you to join the CLISEVE© platform.